

Analysis of Objection Detection and Classification Algorithms on different Embedded Vision Platforms

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Abstract

The term Deep Learning or Deep Neural Network refers to Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) with multi layers. Over the last few decades, it has been considered to be one of the most powerful tools, and has become very popular in the literature as it is able to handle a huge amount of data. It begins with a brief introduction on the history of Machine learning and its representative tool, namely Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). Then we focus on typical generic object detection architectures along with some modifications and useful tricks to improve detection performance further. This report is an analysis on various Object Detection and Classification Algorithms on different hardware platforms, calculating it's frame per second(fps) value, and the "accuracy", performance of different Models available, namely:

1. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN)
 - a. MTCNN
 - b. VGG16, Inception.
2. Haar Cascade.
3. You Only Look Once (YOLO)
4. Single Shot MultiBox Detection (SSD)

Introduction

0.0 A Brief intro to the evolving Machine:

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Deep Learning has been steadily gaining importance due its potential for a broad set of science and industrial applications. The success of deep learning techniques has found many applications, e.g. in the domain of computer vision and natural language understanding. Developing AI applications is a complex task with many challenges related to data collection, model training, and deployment.

With the current pace at which the AI algorithms are evolving and are being developed object Detection through them has now reached a higher accuracy, with lesser computational resource usage.

With the recent advancement of deep learning, the performance of object detection techniques has greatly increased in both speed and accuracy. This has made it possible to run highly accurate object detection with real time speed on modern desktop computer systems. Recently, there has been a growing interest in developing smaller and faster deep neural network architectures suited for embedded devices. This report explores the suitability of running object detection on the Raspberry Pi 3 B+, a popular embedded computer board. Two controlled experiments are conducted where two state of the art object detection models SSD (Single Shot Multibox Detector) and YOLO(You Only Live Once) to test in their performance, accuracy and speed. The results show that the SSD model slightly outperforms YOLO both in speed and accuracy, but with the low processing power that the current generation of Raspberry Pi boards have to offer, none of the two algorithms performs well enough to be viable in applications where high speed is required.

1.0 Machine learning:

Machine learning is a kind of AI that enables computers to think and learn on their own. Machine learning is now one of the most hot topics around the world. Machine learning, well it's just one way of teaching the machine by feeding the large amount of data.

The process of learning begins with observations on data, such as examples, direct experience, or instruction, in order to look for patterns in data and make better decisions in the future based on the examples that we provide. The primary aim is to allow the computers learn automatically without human intervention or assistance and adjust actions accordingly.

Fig1 : Types of Machine Learning [1].

1.1 Evolution of Machine Learning

Today, machine learning is different from what it used to be in the past, due to the emergence of advanced computing technologies. Initially, it had gained momentum due to pattern recognition and the fact that computers did not have to be programmed to execute certain tasks to learn. Many researchers who were interested in Artificial Intelligence (AI) investigated this area further to find out whether computers could really learn from data or not.

Machines learn from the train data and test it on a test set to validate if the given data is good enough to being with, this methodology requires supervision.

Today, machines are now able to apply complicated mathematical calculations to areas, such as big data, at a much faster rate.

1.2 How does Machine Learning work?

To get the maximum value from big data, businesses must know exactly how to pair the right algorithm with a particular tool or process and build machine learning models based on iterative learning processes. Some of the key machines learning algorithms are -

- Random forests
- Neural networks
- Discovery of sequence and associations
- Decision trees
- Mapping of nearest neighbor
- Supporting vector machines
- Boosting and bagging gradient
- Self organizing maps
- Multivariate adaptive regression
- Search Engine Optimization (SEO)
- Principal Components Analysis (PCA)

1.3 Applications of Machine Learning

The value of machine learning technology has been recognized by companies across several industries that deal with huge volumes of data. By leveraging insights obtained from this data, companies are able to work in an efficient manner to control costs as well as get an edge over their competitors. This is how some sectors / domains are implementing machine learning -

- **Financial Services**
- **Marketing and Sales**

- **Oil and Gas**
- **Image Classifications and Detection Algorithms**

2.0 Deep Learning (DL):

With the ability to combine computing power and unique neural networks to learn complex patterns in huge volumes of data, deep learning techniques are used to identify words within sounds, and objects within images. This method is applied to perform complicated tasks like medical diagnosis, business problems, language translation, and other social problems.

Being a top innovative trend, machine learning is now being implemented by several businesses across the globe.

2.1 Why is DL useful?

- Manually designed features are often over-specified, incomplete and take a long time to design and validate
- Learned Features are easy to adapt, fast to learn
- Deep learning provides a very flexible, universal, learnable framework for representing world, visual and linguistic information.
- Can use both unsupervised and supervised methods to perform computations with efficiency under extreme volume of data.

2.2 Applications of DL:-

- **Automatic speech recognition**
- **Image recognition**
- **Bioinformatics**
- **Image restoration**

3.0 Modules Used (For Python):

A. Keras :

Keras is an Open Source Neural Network library written in Python that runs on top of Theano or TensorFlow. It is designed to be modular, fast and easy to use. It was developed by François Chollet, a Google engineer.

Keras doesn't handle low-level computation. Instead, it uses another library to do it, called the "Backend". So Keras is a high-level API wrapper for the low-level API, capable of running on top of TensorFlow, CNTK, or Theano. It works with other libraries and packages such as TensorFlow which makes deep learning easier. Keras was developed to allow for quick experimentation and for fast prototyping.

A1) Backend: Tensorflow 1.14.0 (for Raspberry pi running buster)

TensorFlow is a low level python compatible language used for building neural networks. It's written in a combination of highly-optimized C++ and CUDA (Nvidia's language for programming GPU. Other high level libraries, like Keras, use TF for the back end. Back end simply means Keras passes the heavy lifting to either TF or Theano. Theano is another computational engine for model building.

Tensorflow is vastly used in today's world. Three different groups use machine learning:

1. Researchers
2. Data scientists
3. Programmers

It was built to run on multiple CPUs or GPUs and even mobile operating systems, and it has several wrappers in several languages like Python, C++ or Java.

B. Numpy: NumPy is a Python library for linear algebra. At its core is the NumPy array, a multi-dimensional data structure that can be used to represent vectors and matrices.

C. Pandas: Pandas is used for data manipulation, analysis and cleaning. Python pandas is well suited for different kinds of data, such as:

- Tabular data with heterogeneously-typed columns
- Ordered and unordered time series data
- Arbitrary matrix data with row & column labels
- Unlabelled data

□ Any other form of observational or statistical data sets

D. Open-CV: OpenCV (Open Source Computer Vision) is a library of programming functions mainly aimed at real-time computer vision. In simple language it is library used for Image Processing. It is mainly used to do all the operation related to Images

D1) Computer Vision: Computer vision is an interdisciplinary scientific field that deals with how computers can be made to gain high-level understanding from digital images or videos. From the perspective of engineering, it seeks to automate tasks that the human visual system can do.

E. Matplotlib: To plot the the data-sets and get better data perception.

F. Scikit-learn: To split the datasets that are to be used as train, test and validation sets

4.0 What is Image Classification?

Image Classification is the methodology by which a given image is classified based on the number of classification classes the model is trained on.

For the First task of Object Classification, we use Convolutional Neural Network

CNN starts firstly with detecting the edge, this include the vertical & horizontal edges. The Convolutional Neural network (CNN) is a class of deep learning neural networks. CNNs represent a huge breakthrough in image recognition. They're most commonly used to analyze visual imagery and are frequently working behind the scenes in image classification.

4.1 Convolutional Layers:

A convolutional layer contains a set of filters whose parameters need to be learned. The height and weight of the filters are smaller than those of the input volume. Each filter is convolved with the input

volume to compute an activation map made of neurons. In other words, the filter is slid across the width and height of the input and the dot products between the input and filter are computed at every spatial position. The output volume of the convolutional layer is obtained by stacking the activation maps of all filters along the depth dimension. Since the width and height of each filter is designed to be smaller than the input, each neuron in the activation map is only connected to a small local region of the input volume. In other words, the receptive field size of each neuron is small, and is equal to the filter size. The local connectivity is motivated by the architecture of the animal visual cortex where the receptive fields of the cells are small. The local connectivity of the convolutional layer allows the network to learn filters which maximally respond to a local region of the input, thus exploiting the spatial local correlation of the input (for an input image, a pixel is more correlated to the nearby pixels than to the distant pixels). In addition, as the activation map is obtained by performing convolution between the filter and the input, the filter parameters are shared for all local positions. The weight sharing reduces the number of parameters for efficiency of expression, efficiency of learning, and good generalization.

4.1.1 Elements of a Neural Network :-

Input Layer :- This layer accepts input features. It provides information from the outside world to the network, no computation is performed at this layer, nodes here just pass on the information (features) to the hidden layer.

Hidden Layer :- Nodes of this layer are not exposed to the outer world, they are the part of the abstraction provided by any neural network. Hidden layer performs all sort of computation on the features entered through the input layer and transfer the result to the output layer.

Output Layer :- This layer bring up the information learned by the network to the outer world.

4.2 Convolutional Neural Network (CNN):

A Convolutional Neural Network (ConvNet/CNN) is a Deep Learning algorithm which can take in an input image, assign importance (learnable weights and biases) to various aspects/objects in the image and be able to differentiate one from the other. The pre-processing required in a ConvNet is much lower as compared to other classification algorithms. While in primitive methods filters are hand-engineered, with enough training, ConvNets have the ability to learn these filters/characteristics.

The architecture of a ConvNet is analogous to that of the connectivity pattern of Neurons in the Human Brain and was inspired by the organization of the Visual Cortex. Individual neurons respond to stimuli

only in a restricted region of the visual field known as the Receptive Field. A collection of such fields overlap to cover the entire visual area.

Fig3 : How CNN works [3].

4.2.2 Pooling/subsampling layers :

The pooling/subsampling layer reduces the resolution of the features. It makes the features robust against noise and distortion. There are two ways to do pooling: max pooling and average pooling. In both cases, the input is divided into non-overlapping two-dimensional spaces. For example, in Figure 4, layer 2 is the pooling layer. Each input feature is 28x28 and is divided into 14x14 regions of size 2x2. For average pooling, the average of the four values in the region are calculated. For max pooling, the maximum value of the four values is selected. Figure elaborates the pooling process further. The input is of size 4x4. For 2x2 subsampling, a 4x4 image is divided into four non-overlapping matrices of size 2x2. In the case of max pooling, the maximum value of the four values in the 2x2 matrix is the output. In case of average pooling, the average of the four values is the output.

Fig4 : Pooling/ subsampling layers [4].

4.2.3 CNN Classification process

The Image below describes the steps involved in the full CNN Classification process, regardless of the number of layers and the dimension as well as number of filters applied.

Fig5 : Steps Involved in CNN [5].

4.3 Models experimented with:

4.3.1 VGG16:

It usually refers to a deep convolutional network for object recognition developed and trained by Oxford's renowned Visual Geometry Group (VGG), which achieved very good performance on the ImageNet dataset.

Fig6 : VGG16 Model [6].

4.3.2 Inception:

This model proposes a new idea of creating deep architectures. This approach lets you maintain the “computational budget”, while increasing the depth and width of the network.

4.4 Activation Functions

4.4.1 What is an activation function and why to use them?

Definition of activation function :- Activation function decides, whether a neuron should be activated or not by calculating weighted sum and further adding bias with it. The purpose of the activation function is to introduce non-linearity into the output of a neuron.

Explanation :- It is used to determine the output of neural network like yes or no. It maps the resulting values in between 0 to 1 or -1 to 1 etc. (depending upon the function). The Activation Functions can be basically divided into 2 types-

1. Linear Activation Function
2. Non-linear Activation Functions

4.4.2 Types of Activation Functions:

1.Linear or Identity Activation Function:

Fig7 : Linear Function [7].

□ **Equation :** $f(x) = x$

□ **Range :** (-infinity to infinity)

1. Non-linear Activation Function

- The Nonlinear Activation Functions are the most used activation functions.

Fig 8 : Non-Linear Function [8].

- It makes it easy for the model to generalize or adapt with variety of data and to differentiate between the outputs.

4.4.3 Non Linear Functions:

The Nonlinear Activation Functions are mainly divided on the basis of their **range or curves-**

1. Sigmoid or Logistic Activation Function:

- The Sigmoid Function curve looks like a S-shape.
- The main reason why we use sigmoid function is because it exists between **(0 to 1)**. Therefore, it is especially used for models where we have to **predict the**

Fig9 : Sigmoid Function [9].

probability as an output. Since probability of anything exists only between the range of **0 and 1**, sigmoid is the right choice.

2. Tanh or hyperbolic tangent Activation Function:

- tanh is also like logistic sigmoid but better. The range of the tanh function is from (-1 to 1). tanh is also sigmoidal (s - shaped).

Fig10 : Tanh Function [10].

- The tanh function is mainly used classification between two classes.

3. ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit) Activation Function:

- The ReLU is the most used activation function in the world right now. Since, it is used in almost all the convolutional neural networks or deep learning.

Fig11 : Relu Function [11].

- ReLU is half rectified (from bottom). $f(z)$ is zero when z is less than zero and $f(z)$ is equal to z when z is above or equal to zero.
- **Range:** [0 to infinity)

5.0 Datasets Used:

5.1 MNIST:

The MNIST database (Modified National Institute of Standards and Technology database) is a large database of handwritten digits that is commonly used for training various image processing systems. MNIST is like the "Hello World" of machine learning [12].

Fig12 : MNIST Dataset [12].

5.2 Fashion MNIST:

The Fashion MNIST is a huge database of various images of Fashion items it has 60K train images, and 10k test images. It has 10 classes to classify items from [13].

Fig13 : MNIST Fashion [13].

5.3 Frontal Face Haar Cascade:

Object Detection using Haar feature-based cascade classifiers is an effective method proposed by Paul Viola and Michael Jones in the 2001 paper, "Rapid Object Detection using a Boosted Cascade of Simple Features". It is a machine learning based approach in which a cascade function is trained from a lot of positive and negative images. It is then used to detect objects in other images [14].

Fig14 : Haar Cascade [14].

5.4 Kaggle Dogs and Cats:

We used the collection of Dogs and Cats images , that later used for image classification, after training our own CNN model [15].

Fig15 : Cats and Dogs [15].

5.5 Other Databases For Face recognition:

5.5.1 Face Recognizer:

I used my own images as well as images of an another friend to recognize faces, RealTime. The model was trained on Inception CNN from my training and test set, and for face detection used both MTCNN and Haar-casading was used and efficiency was compared

Fig16: Face Dataset captured from my own laptop webcam

5.5.2 Face Expression:

Used Facial Expression Dataset from Kaggle to determine: Happy, Fear,Sad and Surprised facial expression on RealTime. Compared the accuracy using both MTCNN and Haar Cascade [16].

Fig17 : Expression Dataset [16].

6.0 Setting up the Environment

6.1 System running Debian based OS (Ubuntu 19.04) on i3wm:

Installation Guide for installing the required Packages (using Terminal)

The Installation for all the required packages are done through terminal with the commands below:

Runtime: python 3.7.1

1. apt-get install jupyter notebook (this installs jupyter notebook into our system)
2. pip3 install matplotlib scikit-learn numpy pandas tensorflow==1.14 keras

The 2nd command installs matplotlib,scikit-learn, numpy and tensorflow1.14 (CPU) and keras (backend TensorFlow)

3. apt-get install python3-opencv (this installs openCV into our system)

All the other required Packages are to be installed when an error is received.

If there is permission error we can use “sudo” before the command. It’s much better to use sudo in all the above steps and the steps that are to be used in ARM devices.

6.2 System running on ARM devices namely Raspbian Buster:

Installation Guide for installing the required Packages (using Terminal)

The Installation for all the required packages are done through terminal with the commands below:

Runtime: python 3.7.1

Dependencies

0. apt-get update
1. apt-get install openjdk-8-jdk automake autoconf curl zip unzip libtool swig libpng-dev zlib1g-dev pkg-config git g++ wget xz-utils
2. apt-get install libpython3-all-dev:armhf

3. apt-get install python3-numpy libatlas-base-dev libblas-dev liblapack-dev python3-dev gfortran python3-setuptools python3-scipy python3-h5py

Steps:

1. apt-get install jupyter notebook (this install jupyter notebook into our system)
2. pip3 install matplotlib scikit-learn pandas (installs matplotlib,scikit-learn)
3. apt-get install python3-opencv (installs opencv)

To install tensorflow and keras, these devices require a much longer procedure than simply using “pip” or “apt-get”

0. apt-get update
1. wget https://github.com/lhelontra/tensorflow-on-arm/releases/download/v1.14.0-buster/tensorflow-1.14.0-cp37-none-linux_armv7l.whl
2. pip3 install tensorflow-1.14.0-cp37-none-linux_armv7l.whl
3. pip3 install keras

6.3 Installation of TensorFlow Object Detection API (ARM and Debian System)

1. git clone <https://github.com/tensorflow/models.git>
2. cd models/research/
3. pip3 setup.py build
4. pip3 setup.py install

This is the shortest way to install TFOD in our devices but this way doesn't enable us to update to latest versions later.

7.0 Object Detection

So far what was written was about image classification but not detection. The CNN models used were for classifying the type of thing an object is (determine the class an object is supposed to belong to).

To detect objects, OPENCV is being highly used. The algorithms like Haar-Cascade is widely used for object detection.

7.1 Haar-Cascading

Object Detection using Haar feature-based cascade classifiers is an effective method proposed by Paul Viola and Michael Jones in the 2001 paper, "Rapid Object Detection using a Boosted Cascade of Simple Features". It is a machine learning based approach in which a cascade function is trained from a lot of positive and negative images. It is then used to detect objects in other images.

Fig18 : Haar Cascade Features [14].

Fig19 : Frontal Face Haar Cascade[14].

7.2 Intersection Over Union for object detection:

Generally Intersection over union(IOU) is a measure of overlap between two bounding box . In computer vision it is used for correctly detecting an object. To know object detection first we have to know about object localization. Object localization refers to figuring out where is the object in the picture and showing it with rectangular box. In the world of deep learning Object detection is an active research subject. Objects in an Image/Frame are detected with a simple box bounding around them

7.2.1 Work of IOU:

An algorithm predicts bounding box on the basis of objects that predicted bounding box is compared with ground truth bounding box in the term of IOU.

Intersection over Union is an evaluation metric used to measure the accuracy of an object detector on a particular dataset. Intersection over Union is simply an evaluation metric. Any algorithm that provides predicted bounding boxes as output can be evaluated using IoU.

Fig20 : IOU [17].

To calculate the intersection over union for a class, the following formula was used:

$$IoU_i = \frac{TP_i}{FP_i + FN_i + TP_i} \quad (5.3)$$

where TP is the true positives FP is the false positives and FN is the false negative or all the pixels that should have been labeled with a certain class but was not. For example all pixels that was labeled in the ground truth with car, but were labeled with another class. To calculate the mean intersection over union (mIoU) the mean of all IoUs were calculated.

Fig22 : IOU Formula[18].

7.2.2 Why we use IOU Concept in Object Detection?

Predicted bounding box is judged correctly if the IOU is greater than 0.5 i.e $IOU \geq 0.5$, it's just a human convention you can also choose some other threshold like 0.6 or more for accurate results.

And if the predicted bounding box and ground truth bounding box overlapped perfectly than the **IOU=1**.

Fig23 : Bounding Box Truth [19].

Fig24 : Ground-truth and Predicted BoundingBoxes[20].

7.3 Mostly, Neural Networks are being used for object Detection purposes.

7.3.1 MTCNN (Multi-Task Cascaded Convolutional Networks:For Face Detection)

Multi-task cascaded convolutional networks (MTCNN) is used to realize the multi-view face detection and landmark localization in complex environments. The overall framework includes image preprocessing and three-stage convolutional neural networks. The operation of preprocessing ensures that the given image can be scaled to different scales to build an image pyramid, which is provided for training of the cascaded networks.

In the first stage, it generates candidate windows quickly through the few layers of CNN named Proposal Network (P-Net). Then the candidate windows are calibrated based on the estimated bounding box regression vectors.

7.3.2 YOLO (You Only Look Once)

Yolo stands for You Only Look Once. Here, a single neural network to the full image. This network divides the image into regions and predicts bounding boxes and probabilities for each region. These bounding boxes are weighted by the predicted probabilities. We used a model pretrained on coco dataset

Fig25 : How Yolo Works [21].

7.3.3 SSD (Single Shot MultiBox Detection)

SSD stands for Single Shot MultiBox Detector. SSD's architecture builds on the venerable VGG-16 architecture, but discards the fully connected layers. We used a model pretrained on coco dataset

Fig26 : How SSD Works [22].

Both SSD and YOLO algorithm seem to work under the same basic technique, but SSD is a healthier recommendation. However, if exactness is not too much of a disquiet but you want to go super quick, YOLO will be the best way to move forward. First of all, a visual thoughtfulness of swiftness vs precision trade-off would differentiate them well. SSD is a better option as we are able to run it on a video and the exactness trade-off is very modest. While dealing with large sizes, SSD seems to perform well, but when we look at the accurateness numbers when the object size is small, the performance dips a bit.

7.3.4 CNN for Detection(RCNN: Regional Convolutional Neural Network)

7.3.4(a) RCNN

The R-CNN detector first generates region proposals using an algorithm such as Edge Boxes. The proposal regions are cropped out of the image and resized. Then, the CNN classifies the cropped and resized regions. Finally, the region proposal bounding boxes are refined by a support vector machine (SVM) that is trained using CNN features.

Fig27 : RCNN [23].

7.3.4(b) Fast-RCNN

As in the R-CNN detector , the Fast R-CNN detector also uses an algorithm like Edge Boxes to generate region proposals. Unlike the R-CNN detector, which crops and resizes region proposals, the Fast R-CNN detector processes the entire image. Whereas an R-CNN detector must classify each region, Fast R-CNN pools CNN features corresponding to each region proposal. Fast R-CNN is more efficient than R-CNN, because in the Fast R-CNN detector, the computations for overlapping regions are shared.

Fig28 : Fast-RCNN [24].

7.3.4(c) Faster-RCNN

The Faster R-CNN detector adds a region proposal network (RPN) to generate region proposals directly in the network instead of using an external algorithm like Edge Boxes. The RPN uses Anchor boxes for Object Detection. Generating region proposals in the network is faster and better tuned to your data.

Fig2 9: Faster-RCNN [25].

RPN: Region Proposal Network has a classifier and a regressor. The Classifier gives probabilities of a proposal object and the regressor regresses the coordinate of the proposed object.

Ultimately, RPN is an algorithm that needs to be trained. So we definitely have our Loss Function.

Fig30 : RPN Formula [26].

$$L(\{p_i\}, \{t_i\}) = (1/N_{cls}) \times \sum L_{cls}(p_i, p_i^*) + (\lambda/N_{reg}) \times \sum p_i^* L_{reg}(t_i, t_i^*)$$

Loss Function

8.0 Using the Above on ARM Devices.

8.1 RASPBERRY PI 3 (model B+)

Raspberry pi or Raspi is a computing system that uses a development board, laptop, keyboard, mouse, computer monitor or TV, USB cable, SD card and network cable for its operations.

- Programming is done in languages like Python, C/C++, wiring Pi, PHP.

- It is capable of doing everything that is expected from a computer i.e. from browsing Internet, to playing HD video, to making documents, and playing games.
- It has the ability to interact with outside world and used in many projects relating to weather etc.
- Mainly why it is use dis for its small size which is very useful for using it in drones, iot projects, cars etc.

The basic use of The Raspberry Pi [27] is for educational purpose, it is being used by hardware enthusiasts, teachers, hobbyist, professors, universities etc and also by high school students for their projects related to computer science. Raspberry Pi 3 uses or it can be used to boot up a Linux based Debian OS or Fedora based ARM OS or their is Ubuntu based Linus ARM based OS too.

Fig31: Raspberry Pi 3 B+ [28]

Parts of a Raspberry PI:

- **USB ports** — these are used to connect a mouse and keyboard, also connect other components, such as a USB drive.
- **SD card slot** — this is where the operating system software and your files are stored.
- **Ethernet port** — this is used to connect Raspberry Pi to a network with a cable. Raspberry Pi can also connect to a network via wireless LAN.
- **Audio jack** — to connect headphones or speakers here.
- **HDMI port** — this is to connect the monitor (or projector) that are used to display the output from the Raspberry Pi.
- **Micro USB power connector** — this is where we can connect a power supply.
- **GPIO ports** — these allow you to connect electronic components such as LEDs and buttons to Raspberry Pi.

8.1.1 Setting up a Raspberry Pi (Headless Mode)

8.1.2 First start:

To use a Raspberry pi, it is a necessity to have a monitor, but the this can be avoided by using the “Headless mode” in Raspberry pi.

After writing our memory card with the Raspbian Image we need to add a ssh flag, which enables the ssh interface to our pi.

Operating system: If it was not provided with your kit, you have to create a new SD card with Raspbian Buster on it. We need a micro SD card for this purpose.

8.1.3 INSTALL RASPBIAN

Raspbian Buster is a Linux distribution optimized for Raspberry Pi.

There are two versions of Raspbian:

Lite: without GUI, for embedded systems or to save power or disk space.

Desktop: with GUI, to use it as a classic computer.

Download the required image file and use a software like balenaEtcher to write the image into the sd card, do not forgot to use the flag(ssh).

On the first boot, it will you for a login and password (even by using ssh)

For ssh login we need to use our terminal:

10.202.2.x.xx is the ip of the connected pi.

Here is the default Raspbian user:

Login: pi

Password: raspberry

A terminal window with a dark background. The prompt is 'nyzex@nyrize: ~'. The menu bar shows 'File Edit View Search Terminal Help'. The command being entered is 'ssh pi@10.202.x.xx'.

Fig32: Terminal SSH Command

To enable VNC Server use the command:

```
sudo raspi-config
```

Go to Interfacing options and set VNC Server to enable. After rebooting, we can use VNC Viewer to get a GUI experience of our raspberrypi in our own pc.

8.1.4 Using Object Detection in RPI

8.1.4 Raspberry Pi: Deep learning object detection with OpenCV

It's hard to run computer vision models on Raspberry Pi, and making a portable solution is difficult with deep learning libraries like TensorFlow or PyTorch. For this task, it's almost compulsory to add OpenCV to help pre-process data. It runs much faster than other libraries, and conveniently, it only needs OpenCV in the environment. As a result, OpenCV DNN can run on a CPU's computational power with great speed. The best use case of OpenCV DNN is performing real-time object detection on a Raspberry Pi. This process can run in any environment where OpenCV can be installed.

8.1.4 How Does Object Detection with OpenCV Deep Neural Network (DNN) Work?

OpenCV DNN supports models trained from various frameworks like Caffe and TensorFlow. It also supports various networks architectures based on YOLO, MobileNet-SSD, Inception-SSD, Faster-RCNN Inception, Faster-RCNN ResNet, and Mask-RCNN Inception.

Because OpenCV supports multiple platforms (Android, Raspberry Pi) and languages (C++, Python, and Java), we can use this module for development on many different devices.

8.2 NVIDIA Jetson Nano

Just like Raspberry Pi we have to setup the Jetson Nano and install the required packages, namely:

Keras, Tensorflow, OpenCV, Numpy, Pandas, scikit-learn, matplotlib referring to the Installation guide.

Fig33: Nvidia Jetson Nano[29]

Comparatively Jetson nano has a higher advantage over Raspberry pi: The **Jetson Nano** has a much more powerful processor than the **Raspberry Pi** and the Coral Board with Edge TPU, both of which have Arm Cortex A53-based CPUs, while the **Nano's** uses the more advanced Cortex A57 platform. The **Nano** also has 4GB of RAM as compared to just 1GB on its competitors

So the models for Object Detection will have higher fps and better accuracy when running in Nvidia Jetson Nano than Raspberry pi

	Jetson Nano Dev Board	Raspberry Pi 3A+	Raspberry Pi 3B+
AI Performance	472 GFLOPS	21.5 GFLOPs (est*)	21.4 GFLOPs (est*)
CPU	1.4 GHz 64-bit Quad-Core ARM Cortex-A57 MPCore	1.4 GHz 64-bit Quad-core ARM Cortex-A53	1.4 GHz 64-bit quad-core ARM Cortex-A53
GPU	128-Core Nvidia Maxwell	Broadcom VideoCore IV	Broadcom VideoCore IV
RAM	4GB LPDDR4	512MB LPDDR2 SDRAM	1GB LPDDR2 SDRAM
GPIO Header	40-pin	40-pin	40-pin
Board Dimensions	100 X 79mm	65 X 56mm	85 x 56mm
Wireless	None	Dual-band 802.11ac wireless LAN, Bluetooth 4.2/BLE	Dual-band 802.11ac wireless LAN, Bluetooth 4.2
Ports	4x USB 3.0, wired ethernet 10/100/1000Mbps	1 USB 2.0	4 USB 2.0, Wired Ethernet up to 330 Mbps
Multimedia	2160p30 (H.264)	1080p30 (H.264)	1080p30 (H.264)
Video Output	HDMI, Display Port (4K)	HDMI, Display Serial Interface (DSI)	HDMI, Display Serial Interface (DSI)
Camera Serial Interface	YES	YES	YES
M.2 Key E Slot	YES	NO	NO
Price	\$99	~\$25	~\$35

Fig34 : Jetson Nano vs Raspberry Pi [30].

9.0 Comparison

For the comparison process we will use will use TensorFlow Object Detection API (TFOD) and perform object Detection on the three devices and see the FPS (Frames per second) rate.

9.0.1 The experimental setup for Object Detection:

1. PC and RPI

Fig35: Interfacing RPI B+ with laptop

The Laptop used is ASUS FX504 with i5 8th Gen Processor, 16 GB DDR4 2666Mhz RAM

The RPI is connected to Laptop using Ethernet and powered using USB Cable.

The video is recorded using Pi Camera.

Pi Camera:

Another contributing factor to this choice was the availability of the Pi camera module, which can capture high-definition video as well as stills and requires the user to simply update Raspberry's firmware to the latest version. It can easily be used in OpenCV based applications.

Fig36: Pi Camera.[30]

Fig37: Pi Camera Port in Raspberry Pi.[31]

To use the Pi Camera, it is necessary to set

1. Connect the camera into the “Camera Module Port”
2. Enable Camera Inface on RaspberryPi Configuration
3. `raspistill -o Desktop/Image.jpg`

The 3rd command captures an images and stores it on Desktop.

This is how we set up the picamera for use.

Fig38: PiCamera V2 connection with RPI B+

2.NVIDIA Jetson Nano

Fig39: NVIDIA Jetson Nano connected to monitor with basic setup

NVIDIA Jetson Nano is directly connected to a monitor through HDMI Cable and with the basic setup with an external camera attached to it through Universal Serial Bus (USB).

Fig40: Logitech USB Camera [32]

9.1 TFOD on PC

Specs:

i5 8th Gen, 16GB Ram

GPU: NVIDIA 1050ti

We see that we achieve 300 fps. Tensorflow on CPU, The Model used for the comparison is SSDLite-Mobilenet

Fig41 : Using TensorFlow Object Detection on PC.

9.2 TFOD on Raspberry Pi 3 B+

Specs:

Broadcom BCM2837B0 quad-core A53 (ARMv8) 64-bit @ 1.4GHz, 1GB LPDDR2 SDRAM.

GPU: Broadcom Videocore-IV.

Fig42: Using TensorFlow Objection Detection on RPI

We see that we achieve fps lesser than 1, even at a lower resolution, which is also laggy.

9.3 TFOD on NVIDIA Jetson Nano

Specs:

Feature	Specification
GPU	128-core NVIDIA Maxwell™
CPU	64-bit Quad-core ARM A57 (1.43 GHz)
Memory	4 GB 64-bit LPDDR4 (25.6 GB/s bandwidth)
Networking	10/100/1000 Mbit Ethernet
Camera	12 MIPI CSI-2 DPHY 1.1 lanes (1.5 Gb/s), Dual ISB (1.5 Gpix/s)
Module Mechanical Specifications	69.6 mm x 45 mm, 260-pin SODIMM connector
Module Interfaces	
USB	3x USB 2.0 ports and 1x USB 3.0 port
PCIe	1 (x1/x2/x4)
Camera	CSI 3 x4 or 2 x4 + 2 x2 or 1 x4 + 3 x2
Display	HDMI 2.0 or DP 1.2, eDP 1.4, DSI (1 x2) 2 simultaneous displays
Audio (I2S)	2x
SDIO	1x
Gigabit Ethernet	yes
I2C	3x
UART	3x
SPI	2x
Module Mechanical Specifications	69.6 mm x 45 mm, 260-pin SODIMM connector
Fan	PWM and Tach input
DevKit Interfaces	
USB	4x USB 3.0 Type A ports, 1x USB Micro-B
Display	HDMI 2.0, DisplayPort 1.2
40-Pin Header	GPIOs, I2C, I2S, SPI, PWM, UART
Camera	MIPI-CSI camera Connector
Storage	MicroSD card slot
Other IO	M.2 Wi-Fi card slot, Gigabit Ethernet, Fan connector, PoE connector, UART header

Fig43: Nvidia Jetson Nano Specifications[33]

Fig44: TensorFlow Object Detection on NVIDIA Jetson Nano.

We see that we got around 23 fps, which is 20x better than RPI.

10.0 Assignments

Assignment 1:

The example below creates a convolutional neural network that expects grayscale images with the square size of 256x256 pixels, with one convolutional layer with 32 filters, each with the size of 3x3 pixels, a max pooling layer, and a binary classification output layer.

```
# cnn with single convolutional, pooling and output layer
from keras.models import Sequential
from keras.layers import Conv2D
from keras.layers import MaxPooling2D
from keras.layers import Flatten
from keras.layers import Dense
# create model
model = Sequential()
# add convolutional layer
model.add(Conv2D(32, (3,3), input_shape=(256, 256, 1)))
model.add(MaxPooling2D())
model.add(Flatten())
model.add(Dense(1, activation='sigmoid'))
model.summary()
```

Result :

```
conv2d_1 (Conv2D)                (None, 254, 254, 32)    320
max_pooling2d_1 (MaxPooling2D)   (None, 127, 127, 32)    0
conv2d_2 (Conv2D)                (None, 125, 125, 12)   3468
max_pooling2d_2 (MaxPooling2D)   (None, 62, 62, 12)     0
flatten_1 (Flatten)              (None, 46128)          0
dense_1 (Dense)                  (None, 1)              46129
-----
Total params: 49,917
Trainable params: 49,917
Non-trainable params: 0
```

Fig45: Model Summary

Result after changing the values of layers :

```
Layer (type)                Output Shape              Param #
-----
conv2d_1 (Conv2D)           (None, 38, 38, 32)       320
max_pooling2d_1 (MaxPooling2D) (None, 19, 19, 32)       0
conv2d_2 (Conv2D)           (None, 17, 17, 12)      3468
max_pooling2d_2 (MaxPooling2D) (None, 8, 8, 12)        0
flatten_1 (Flatten)         (None, 768)              0
dense_1 (Dense)             (None, 1)                769
-----
Total params: 4,557
Trainable params: 4,557
Non-trainable params: 0
ψ ~/Desktop/III_Indore/cnn/:
```

Fig46: Model Summary after chnaging of values

Assignment 2 :

In this lesson, you will discover how to use a pre-trained model to classify photographs of objects. Deep convolutional neural network models may take days, or even weeks, to train on very large datasets. A way to short-cut this process is to re-use the model weights from pre-trained models that were developed for standard computer vision benchmark datasets, such as the ImageNet image recognition tasks. The example below uses the VGG-16 pre-trained model to classify photographs of objects into one of 1,000 known classes. The example below will load the photograph and output a prediction, classifying the object in the photograph.

Note: The first time you run the example, the pre-trained model will have to be downloaded, which is a few hundred megabytes and may take a few minutes based on the speed of your internet connection.

```
# example of using a pre-trained model as a classifier
from keras.preprocessing.image import load_img
from keras.preprocessing.image import img_to_array
from keras.applications.vgg16 import preprocess_input
from keras.applications.vgg16 import decode_predictions
from keras.applications.vgg16 import VGG16
# load an image from file
image = load_img('dog.jpg', target_size=(224, 224))
# convert the image pixels to a numpy array
image = img_to_array(image)
# reshape data for the model
image = image.reshape((1, image.shape[0], image.shape[1],
image.shape[2]))
# prepare the image for the VGG model
image = preprocess_input(image)
# load the model
model = VGG16()
# predict the probability across all output classes
yhat = model.predict(image)
# convert the probabilities to class labels
label = decode_predictions(yhat)
# retrieve the most likely result, e.g. highest probability
label = label[0][0]
# print the classification
print('%s (%.2f%%)' % (label[1], label[2]*100))
```

Result 1: Giving the input picture of a Dog

```
WARNING:tensorflow:From C:\Users\User\Anaconda3\lib\site-package
f.ConfigProto is deprecated. Please use tf.compat.v1.ConfigProto

Downloading data from https://storage.googleapis.com/download.te
40960/35363 [=====] - 0s 3us/step
Doberman (33.59%)
```

Result 2: Here we changed the picture from a Doberman do to a Boxer dog and the machine is able is detect it wth 99.5% accuracys

```
# convert the probabilities to class labels
label = decode_predictions(yhat)
# retrieve the most likely result, e.g. highest probability
label = label[0][0]
# print the classification
print('%s (%.2f%%)' % (label[1], label[2]*100))

boxer (99.53%)
```

Result 3: Running the model on a given picture.

The image shows a Google Colab notebook interface. On the left, there is a photograph of a black and tan dog, likely a Rottweiler, standing in a grassy field. On the right, the notebook's code editor is visible, showing Python code that uses TensorFlow and VGG16 for image classification. The code includes steps for loading the image, preprocessing it, loading the VGG16 model, and decoding the predictions. The output of the code is displayed at the bottom of the cell, showing the classification result: "Doberman (33.59%)".

Fig47 : Using VGG16 to make multiclass Classification

Assignment 3:

In this lesson, you will discover how to train and evaluate a convolutional neural network for image classification. The Fashion-MNIST clothing classification problem is a new standard dataset used in computer vision and deep learning. It is a dataset comprised of 60,000 small square 28x28 pixel grayscale images of items of 10 types of clothing, such as shoes, t-shirts, dresses, and more. The example below loads the dataset, scales the pixel values, then fits a convolutional neural network on the training dataset and evaluates the performance of the network on the test dataset.

```
# fit a cnn on the fashion mnist dataset
from keras.datasets import fashion_mnist
from keras.utils import to_categorical
from keras.models import Sequential
from keras.layers import Conv2D
from keras.layers import MaxPooling2D
from keras.layers import Dense
from keras.layers import Flatten
# load dataset
(trainX, trainY), (testX, testY) = fashion_mnist.load_data()
# reshape dataset to have a single channel
trainX = trainX.reshape((trainX.shape[0], 28, 28, 1))
testX = testX.reshape((testX.shape[0], 28, 28, 1))
# convert from integers to floats
trainX, testX = trainX.astype('float32'), testX.astype('float32')
# normalize to range 0-1
trainX, testX = trainX / 255.0, testX / 255.0
# one hot encode target values
trainY, testY = to_categorical(trainY), to_categorical(testY)
# define model
model = Sequential()
model.add(Conv2D(32, (3, 3), activation='relu', kernel_initializer='he_uniform',
input_shape=(28, 28, 1)))
model.add(MaxPooling2D())
model.add(Flatten())
model.add(Dense(100, activation='relu', kernel_initializer='he_uniform'))
model.add(Dense(10, activation='softmax'))
model.compile(optimizer='adam', loss='categorical_crossentropy',
metrics=['accuracy'])
# fit model
model.fit(trainX, trainY, epochs=10, batch_size=32, verbose=2)
# evaluate model
loss, acc = model.evaluate(testX, testY, verbose=0)
print(loss, acc)
```

Result :

```
Epoch 1/10
- 11s - loss: 0.3743 - accuracy: 0.8655
Epoch 2/10
- 11s - loss: 0.2535 - accuracy: 0.9082
Epoch 3/10
- 11s - loss: 0.2091 - accuracy: 0.9224
Epoch 4/10
- 11s - loss: 0.1776 - accuracy: 0.9340
Epoch 5/10
- 11s - loss: 0.1501 - accuracy: 0.9446
Epoch 6/10
- 12s - loss: 0.1294 - accuracy: 0.9521
Epoch 7/10
- 11s - loss: 0.1092 - accuracy: 0.9605
Epoch 8/10
- 11s - loss: 0.0927 - accuracy: 0.9665
Epoch 9/10
- 11s - loss: 0.0804 - accuracy: 0.9701
Epoch 10/10
- 11s - loss: 0.0676 - accuracy: 0.9747
0.3788396430581808 0.9028000235557556
```

Fig48: The Training of the model

Here, a picture is loaded and predicted.

```
2020-01-10 13:55:00.040869: I tensorflow/core/platform/cpu_feature_guard.cc:142] Your CPU supports instructions that this TensorFlow binary was not compiled to use: AVX2 FMA
2020-01-10 13:55:00.063015: I tensorflow/core/platform/profile_utils/cpu_utils.cc:94] CPU Frequency: 229 996000 Hz
2020-01-10 13:55:00.064061: I tensorflow/compiler/xla/service/service.cc:168] XLA service 0x51db30 exec using computations on platform Host. Devices:
2020-01-10 13:55:00.064114: I tensorflow/compiler/xla/service/service.cc:175] StreamExecutor device (0): <undefined>, <undefined>
2020-01-10 13:55:00.091819: W tensorflow/compiler/jit/mark_for_compilation_pass.cc:1412] (One-time warning): Not using XLA/CPU for cluster because envvar TF_XLA_FLAGS=--tf_xla_cpu_global_jit was not set. If you want XLA/CPU, either set that envvar, or use experimental_jit_scope to enable XLA/CPU. To confirm that XLA is active, pass --xrt_device=xla to the compilation cache=1 (as a proper command-line flag, not via TF_XLA_FLAGS) or set the envvar XLA_FLAGS=--xla_hlo_profile.
WARNING:tensorflow:From /usr/local/lib/python3.7/dist-packages/keras/backend/tensorflow_backend.py:422: The name tf.global_variables is deprecated. Please use tf.compat.v1.global_variables instead.
0.34822238972647666 0.9896999764442444
/usr/local/lib/python3.7/dist-packages/keras_preprocessing/image/utils.py:184: UserWarning: grayscale is deprecated. Please use color_mode = "grayscale"
warnings.warn("grayscale is deprecated. Please use
Class: [2]
```

Fig49: Predicted Value

Prediction returned class = 2.

In Fashion-MNIST class [2] is Pullover

Fig50: Test Image

11.0 Other Projects

11.1 Facial Expression

The model is trained by using Facial Expression Dataset from Kaggle.

Obtained accuracy of about 65%

```
...  
Epoch 50/50  
225/225 [=====] - 30s 132ms/step - loss:  
0.6723 - acc: 0.7499 - val_loss: 1.1159 - val_acc: 0.6384  
Epoch 00050: val acc did not improve from 0.65221
```

During the project both mtcnn and opencv haar-cascades, **the results showed a better face detection on using mtcnn**, though the recognition was same in both cases.

Fig51: Emotion Prediction

11.2 Face Recognizer

The model was trained using my own pictures using webcam. The dataset had 1500 pictures of me for training set and 800 pictures for test set.

Here, too both haarcascade and MTCNN was used for face detection, **using MTCNN showed a better result.**

Due to lesser amount of training data and data was captured under a similar situation, the model isn't accurate.

Fig52: Face Recognized

11.3 MNIST RealTime Recognizer

Here, a model of MNIST handwritten dataset from Kaggle is trained and will be used to perform realtime recognition of digit from webcam or android camera.

11.4 OpenCV based ImageAI realtime object Detection Yolov3 and Yolo-tiny in PC and rpi

Pretrained model on cocoapi is used with ImageAI and openCV to perform realtime objection detection.

The module imageAI is for static detection only, but when opencv is applied to continuous open, detect and write image frame by frame, we get “real-time object detection”

Drawback: High Resource usage, as seen on the image.

This module couldn't run in RPI 3 B+

Fig53 : Object Detection using ImageAI [34].

Advantage: A few lines of code was used to perform the object Detection

The future projects related to the topics learnt will be put into the GitHub repository:

<https://github.com/Quanta-of-solitude/IITI>

Future Projects can include:

- **Attendance System**
- **Traffic Monitoring**
- **Surveillance**

12.0 CONCLUSION

The four weeks at IIT Indore was a great experience. The path to begin DeepLearning was properly pointed out to me and with the help of the members of the lab the concepts were highly simplified, hence making it a fun, and interesting experience.

The study of Neural Networks shaped my way of thinking, which has now enabled me to come up with new ideas; which I can apply to my future projects.

Along with the theoretical knowledge received, I got to have the hands-on experience with various hardware devices namely: Raspberry Pi and NVIDIA Jetson Nano, this has boosted my skills by a long shot indeed.

With these knowledge now in my arsenal I also have made new friends and formed a bond with my professors and instructors, I sincerely hope they will help me up with the future aspects too.

IIT Indore is an awesome place for internships because it provides numerous benefits and advantages. They provided us with accommodation, facilities such as Wi-Fi access, table for work etc. The treatment by the college is equitable and professional. I have learnt a great deal from different units and people.

I am thankful to my supervisors Dr. Bhupesh Kumar Lad and Dr. Vishal Sharma for the experience and tutoring. They also helped me with the concepts and simplified my learning curve, also provided guidance to me whenever I needed. I think four weeks internship was an adequate time to start the basic introduction to the different algorithms and techniques for Object Detection, though a longer period would have been much more fruitful because there's still a lot to learn from my supervisors. I will encourage my friends to grab the opportunity to do internship in IITI as it will help them to identify their strength, abilities, weaknesses and more as it has helped me to do so.

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